

1
2
3 **Introducing multi-energy ratios as an alternative to multi-energy**
4 **calibration for Br determination *via* high-resolution continuum**
5 **source graphite furnace molecular absorption spectrometry. A**
6 **case study**
7
8
9
10
11
12

13 **Raúl Garde, Flávio V. Nakadi,* Esperanza García-Ruiz and Martín**
14 **Resano***
15
16
17

18
19 Department of Analytical Chemistry, Aragón Institute of Engineering Research
20 (I3A), University of Zaragoza, Pedro Cerbuna 12, 50009, Zaragoza, Spain. E-
21 mail: mresano@unizar.es; E-mail: flavionakadi@gmail.com
22
23
24
25

26 **Abstract**
27

28 This manuscript explores the advantages of using multi-signal calibration
29 approaches for the determination of non-metals *via* high-resolution continuum
30 source graphite furnace molecular absorption spectrometry (HR CS GFMAS),
31 targeting Br as an example. Besides multi-energy calibration (MEC), a novel
32 approach deriving from it, multi-energy ratios (MER), is introduced and compared
33 under different conditions. This approach makes use of the same data but in a
34 different way, such that no linear regression is performed; instead, ratios are
35 calculated.
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45

46 The article investigates the potential errors deriving from the use of
47 amounts of spike dissimilar from the sample content, leading to too high (close to
48 1) or too low (close to 0) slopes/ratios, setting the best conditions in terms of
49 precision and accuracy for the intended determination in the range of approx. 0.5
50 to 0.6. Also, situations where the use of MER could be recommended over MEC
51 are identified: namely when only a few transitions of sufficient sensitivity and free
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 from overlaps are available or else, many transitions but of similar sensitivity,
4 which may occur when HR CS GFMS is deployed. Otherwise, for multiple
5 transitions covering a wider sensitivity range, use of linear regression and thus,
6 of MEC, seems favoured, as a better precision can be achieved. The calculation
7 of limits of detection and quantification for both approaches is also discussed.
8
9

10
11
12 It is finally further demonstrated that these multi-signal strategies help in
13 solving chemical interferences, which very often hamper the determination of
14 non-metals with HR CS GFMS, and they do so in a simple way, without the
15 need for laborious work or for the preparation of several standards and sample
16 aliquots, therefore making them a very intriguing option when this technique is
17 deployed.
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1. Introduction

Quantitative methods of analysis depend on the relation between the signal of the analyte and the concentration of such analyte in a sample, a relation that should be either known in advance *via* theoretical considerations without the use of any analytical standard of known concentration (absolute methods), or else experimentally established using analytical standard(s). In instrumental analysis, many efforts have been directed at the development of absolute methods.^{1,2} However, in the end, the most popular strategies depend on external calibration based on linear regression statistics, a method that fits the data to a linear curve minimizing the error in the Y-axis (analytical signal), since the error in the X-axis (analyte concentration or total amount) is considered as negligible in comparison. But the presence of the matrix in the sample can affect the analytical signal, due to the occurrence of interferences. Use of internal standards is a widely accepted approach to minimize such interferences to some extent, although it cannot always be used as monitoring two different signals at the same time sometimes is not possible. Alternative calibration approaches such as standard addition or matrix-matching show the potential to correct for some of these matrix-related interferences.³⁻⁶ These approaches provide some benefits but also come with some drawbacks, such as requiring more effort, resulting in a lower sample throughput, and, in the case of matrix-matching, the necessity to know or determine the presence of some compounds to replicate such matrix. Alternatively, in the case of using techniques in which the signal of different isotopes can be selectively measured, isotope dilution is a powerful approach. Unlike the methods discussed before, isotope dilution mass spectrometry does not rely on linear regression. Instead, the well-known natural abundances of the

1
2
3 stable isotopes are considered “true”, or else, their relation can be experimentally
4 measured. A spike of the target species that shows a substantially different
5 isotopic composition from the natural one is also required. Typically, by
6 measuring two isotopes free from spectral overlaps of the target species in an
7 aliquot of the sample, an aliquot of the spike and an aliquot of an isotopically
8 equilibrated mixture of sample plus spike (blend), the signals from such isotopes
9 can be ratioed and from those values the analyte content in the sample can be
10 derived.⁷ This methodology is considered a primary analytical technique due to
11 its high precision and potential to correct for matrix effects.^{8,9} However, it is not
12 always possible to make use of it, among other reasons simply because in
13 elemental analysis the target analyte may not possess more than one stable
14 isotope.

15
16 Recently, a new calibration methodology has been introduced by Virgilio *et al.*¹⁰
17 This strategy exploits the monitorization of several “channels” (*i.e.*, energetic
18 transitions; isotopes; polyatomic species) of the same analyte of two aliquots:
19 sample spiked with a blank (sample+blank) and sample spiked with a known
20 amount of analyte (sample+standard). By plotting the signals from such aliquots
21 and performing linear regression, the mass or concentration of the sample can
22 be calculated using the slope of such linear regression (see section 3.1.1. for
23 more details).

24
25 This represents an ingenious approach with potential to overcome matrix
26 interferences without the need for performing extra measurements. In fact, the
27 number of measurements is actually lower than those needed for a conventional
28 external calibration (unless a one-point calibration is carried out). The advantage

1
2
3 of obtaining multiple signals from every aliquot replaces the need to prepare and
4
5 measure many standards.
6

7 This approach was labelled multi-energy calibration (MEC) and it has been used
8
9 for atomic emission techniques such as inductively coupled plasma optical
10
11 emission spectrometry (ICP OES),¹⁰ microwave-induced plasma optical emission
12
13 spectrometry (MIP OES)^{10,11} and laser-induced breakdown spectrometry,¹²⁻¹⁶ as
14
15 well as for atomic absorption processes, namely high-resolution continuum
16
17 source flame atomic absorption spectrometry (HR CS FAAS),¹⁰ high-resolution
18
19 continuum source molecular absorption spectrometry (HR CS MAS)¹⁷ and
20
21 molecular absorption in the ultraviolet-visible region of the spectra, in addition to
22
23 fluorescence.¹⁸
24
25
26
27

28 The same principle has also been applied to inductively coupled plasma mass
29
30 spectrometry (ICP-MS) by monitoring different isotopes from the same
31
32 element,^{19,20} and then it has been referred to as multi-isotope calibration.
33
34

35 Moreover, since not all elements possess various stable nuclides, the use of a
36
37 reaction cell to form and measure different adducts from the only nuclide available
38
39 in such cases has also been proposed, taking advantage of the potential of
40
41 inductively coupled plasma tandem mass spectrometry in this regard.^{21,22} This
42
43 certainly represents an innovative approach to further expand the use of this
44
45 calibration approach, and then it has been named as multispecies calibration.²³
46
47
48

49 Most of these papers demonstrate the application of this multi-signal calibration
50
51 concept to develop applications with different techniques, further proving its
52
53 promising performance. However, owing to its novelty, there is a lack of
54
55 fundamental knowledge regarding its optimal use. For instance, as will be shown
56
57 in section 3.1.1, the relationship between the slope of the regression and the
58
59
60

1
2
3 concentration of the analyte is not linear, which implies that the amount of spike
4 added may play an important role in terms of precision and accuracy.
5
6

7
8 A very recent work by Virgilio *et al.* has investigated some of these fundamental
9 aspects, namely how to properly calculate the limits of detection (LOD) and
10 quantification (LOQ) as well as indicating a working range for the slope in which
11 good accuracy and precision are expected.²⁴ While this is a welcome addition,
12 we believe there are still fundamental aspects that require further investigation
13 for an optimal application of the methodology to each particular situation.
14
15
16
17
18
19

20
21 In our view, one of the techniques that can benefit more from the use of this
22 intriguing calibration strategy is HR CS MAS in general and, in particular, when
23 graphite furnace is used (HR CS GFMAS) as vaporizer.^{25,26} The reason for this is
24 that such technique is very prone to suffer from chemical interferences deriving
25 from the presence of other elements in the sample. Generally, the vaporization
26 process is often not as straightforward as a pure atomization process mostly
27 based on temperature, and the presence of many other species may result in the
28 formation of other compounds different from the targeted one.^{27,28} Interestingly,
29 while commercially available HR CS AAS instrumentation offers the potential to
30 monitor only a narrow part of the spectrum simultaneously, which affects the
31 multi-element possibilities of the technique,^{29,30} when molecular species are
32 measured different rotational or vibrational transitions superimposed to the
33 electronic transitions are monitored,^{31,32} and the resolution of the instrumentation
34 is often sufficient to resolve such transitions. In other words, when HR CS MAS
35 is used, often many lines can be fully simultaneously monitored, which can make
36 MEC an ideal strategy to minimize matrix effects as well as to increase sample
37 throughput. In this aspect, MEC has only been applied to HR CS MAS once, when
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 Vieira *et al.*¹⁷ studied the determination of N, P and S in fertilizers (N and P) and
4 commercial salts (S and N) by HR CS FMAS *via* the measurement of the
5 molecules NO, PO and CS, respectively, and the determination of Cl in milk *via*
6 the measurement of CaCl by HR CS GFMAS, with positive results.
7
8
9

10
11
12 This study has selected the CaBr molecule to develop a method for the
13 determination of Br using HR CS GFMAS, with the goal to discuss fundamental
14 aspects related with the application of MEC as calibration approach (error
15 propagation as a function of the slope selected, selection of lines, linearity and
16 calculation of LODs) when such technique is applied. Moreover, another different
17 approach, similar to MEC in terms of the aliquots that need to be measured, but
18 different in terms of data processing is introduced. This new strategy can be
19 considered as inspired by isotope dilution as it is also based on calculating ratios
20 (see section 3.1.2.), and the name proposed for it is multi-energy ratios (MER).
21
22

23
24 The selection of both Br as analyte and of CaBr as target molecule where
25 certainly not fortuitous. The formation of this molecule or of any other Br molecule
26 is easily affected by chemical interferences,^{27,33} so it is a challenging problem to
27 solve with MEC or MER approaches, as will be discussed. Moreover, CaBr offers
28 transitions of different characteristics in two different spectral regions, such that
29 pros and cons of these two approaches can be properly evaluated.
30
31
32

33 **2. Experimental**

34 **2.1. Instrumentation**

35
36 All the measurements were carried out using a contrAA 800G high-resolution
37 continuum source atomic absorption spectrometer (Analytik Jena AG, Jena,
38 Germany) equipped with transversally-heated graphite tube atomizers that
39 incorporated a platform (Analytik Jena AG). The main details about this type of
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 instrument can be found elsewhere.²⁵ The samples and reagents were pipetted
4
5 automatically with an autosampler ASGF (Analytik Jena AG).
6

7 8 **2.2. Standards, reagents and samples**

9
10 The solutions were prepared with reagents of analytical grade or higher purity.
11
12 Deionized water purified by a Milli-Q system (Millipore, Bedford, USA) was used
13
14 for the solutions. Nitric acid 65% Suprapur® (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) was
15
16 diluted to 1% v v⁻¹ to prepare the chemical modifier and molecule-forming reagent
17
18 solutions.
19

20
21 A 1000 mg L⁻¹ Br standard (Merck) was used to prepare all the Br aqueous
22
23 standard solutions, as sample and/or spike. A Pd standard solution 10 g L⁻¹
24
25 (Merck) was diluted in order to achieve a final mass of 30 µg (5 µL of 6 g L⁻¹ Pd
26
27 solution). Calcium carbonate with purity of >99.0% (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis,
28
29 USA) was dissolved in HNO₃ 1% v v⁻¹ until a final concentration of 3% m v⁻¹ Ca
30
31 was obtained, then 5 µL were pipetted together with the sample and chemical
32
33 modifier (150 µg Ca). The interference study was carried out by proper dilutions
34
35 of a Cl standard solution 1000 mg L⁻¹ (Merck).
36
37
38
39

40 The certified reference material (CRM) of water Anions - Whole Volume
41
42 QC3060 (Lot#LRAB9707, Sigma-Aldrich) was analyzed to evaluate the accuracy
43
44 of the method and the impact of interfering species.
45
46

47 **2.3. Measurement conditions**

48
49 Two CaBr vibronic transitions were monitored, X²Σ → A²Π (0,0) and X²Σ →
50
51 B²Σ (1,0), around 625.0 and 600.5 nm, respectively. Preliminary tests comparing
52
53 peak height and peak area, with 1, 3 or 5 detector pixels in both cases, showed
54
55 that using 5 pixels and measuring peak areas (integrated absorbance) resulted
56
57
58
59
60

in better linearities obtained *via* MEC. Thus, such approach was selected for this study.

For all the measurements, unless otherwise noted, the temperature program and general conditions of the graphite furnace were adapted from Flórez & Resano³³ and are shown in **Table 1**. Several peaks (wavelengths) of both transitions were evaluated, so they were named after their detection pixel for practical purposes, as shown in **Table 2**. **Figure 1** shows the spectra (average of 68 spectra obtained during 5 s of detection time) of the CaBr diatomic molecule at both wavelengths, labelling the peaks studied with their respective detection pixel.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Theoretical background

3.1.1. Multi-energy calibration (MEC)

Multi-energy calibration is a novel calibration approach that has been proposed by Virgilio *et al.*¹⁰ for use in optical spectrometry. The calculations corresponding to such approach can be explained as follows: considering the general correlation found in spectrometric techniques, at a specific wavelength (λ_i), the analytical signal $I(\lambda_i)^{Sam}$ is linearly proportional, by the proportionality constant m , to the analyte concentration C^{Sam} , as written in equation 1. Obviously, the addition of a spike C^{Std} results in an increase in the analyte level and the instrumental response should also vary accordingly, $I(\lambda_i)^{Sam + Std}$ (see equation 2).

$$I(\lambda_i)^{Sam} = mC^{Sam} \quad (1)$$

$$I(\lambda_i)^{Sam + Std} = m(C^{Sam} + C^{Std}) \quad (2)$$

Combining both equations 1 and 2, equation 3 is obtained, which relates the analytical signal of a sample and a spiked sample with the concentration of the analyte in the sample and in the spike. This equation is convenient because this relation is true when measuring different transitions, occurring at different wavelengths, which possess different sensitivities. Therefore, if the sample and sample+standard can be measured at different wavelengths, and their data are plotted as $I(\lambda_i)^{Sam}$ versus $I(\lambda_i)^{Sam + Std}$, a linear plot should be obtained with a slope S equal to $(C^{Sam}/C^{Sam} + C^{Std})$, as shown in equation 4. Rearranging such equation, equation 5 is obtained, which expresses the concentration of the sample as a function of the slope (measurable) and the concentration of the spike (which should be known in advance).

$$I(\lambda_i)^{Sam} = I(\lambda_i)^{Sam + Std} \left[\frac{C^{Sam}}{C^{Sam} + C^{Std}} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$Slope = S = \frac{C^{Sam}}{C^{Sam} + C^{Std}} \quad (4)$$

$$C^{Sam} = \frac{SC^{Std}}{(1 - S)} \quad (5)$$

The previous works about MEC usually mix sample+blank (1:1) to balance the dilution originated when the spike is added (1:1). This strategy is useful because the addition of a spike solution into the sample leads to a dilution of the latter. Therefore, if the same volume of both blank and spike solutions is added to the sample, the dilution would be the same in both cases, making it possible to carry out a straightforward calculation, as shown in equation 5.

However, this is not an issue for HR CS GFMS because this technique typically uses a known-volume. Therefore, it is possible to use the equation 5 also for masses instead of for concentrations. In this work, the amount of analyte

(bromine) will be given as mass, although the terminology C^{Sam} and C^{Std} will be maintained for simplicity. Thus, in the current work, the blank was measured separately and subtracted from the sample and sample+standard analytical signals.

Since the relation evaluated by MEC is the instrumental intensity of the sample *versus* the intensity of the sample+standard, the slope values should be between ~ 0 (infinite amount of spike added) and ~ 1 (infinitesimal amount of spike added). In this context, one could predict the theoretical bias of the concentration finally obtained as a function of the deviation of the slope experimentally calculated.

Such deviation can be expressed as the absolute slope measurement error, e_S , which ultimately contributes to the deviation of C^{Sam} , e_C , as described in equation 6.

$$(C^{Sam} \pm e_C) = \frac{(S \pm e_S)C^{Std}}{[1 - (S \pm e_S)]} \quad (6)$$

The theoretical value of C^{Sam} is obtained when $e_S = 0$, *i.e.*, the relation between C^{Sam} and C^{Std} is exactly $(S/1-S)$. Assuming that the variations of C^{Std} are practically negligible, then the deviation when calculating C^{Sam} , *i.e.* e_C , exists due the deviation in the estimation of S , *i.e.* e_S , as detailed in equation 6.

Therefore, it is possible to estimate how the e_S value will affect the concentration bias with equation 7. Basically, the bias reflects the difference between theoretical and experimentally obtained values for $(S/1-S)$, which directly translates into a difference of C^{Sam} . Thus, the % of bias for C^{Sam} can be written as:

$$bias_{C^{±sam}}(\%) = \frac{\left\{ \frac{(S \pm e_S)}{[1 - (S \pm e_S)]} \right\} - \left(\frac{S}{1 - S} \right)}{\left(\frac{S}{1 - S} \right)} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

It can be noticed (see equation 6) that the upper limit of e_S value will lead to the upper limit of e_C and concentration bias, e_C^+ and $bias_{C^{±sam}}$, respectively. Thus, equation 7 can be further developed into equation 8 (see Supplementary information for more details).

$$bias_{C^{±sam}}(\%) = \frac{e_S}{S(1 - S - e_S)} \times 100\% \quad (8)$$

The lower limit, $bias_{C^{\bar{s}am}}$, can be calculated analogously, resulting in equation 9 (see Supplementary information). Both equations 8 and 9 can be unified and they become equation 10, which enables the calculation of both the upper and lower concentration biases, just applying “+” (for the upper limit) or “–” (for the lower limit) where “ \pm ” is indicated. For instance, a 5% deviation of the slope, for a slope value of 0.5 (thus $S=0.5$ and $e_S = 0.025$) will ultimately result in a concentration bias of 10.5% and –9.5% (depending on whether the deviation is positive or negative, respectively). It is noteworthy that the relation between e_S and $bias_{C^{±sam}}$ is neither linear nor symmetric.

$$bias_{C^{\bar{s}am}}(\%) = \frac{-e_S}{S(1 - S + e_S)} \times 100\% \quad (9)$$

$$bias_{C^{±sam}}(\%) = \frac{\pm e_S}{S(1 - S \pm e_S)} \times 100\% \quad (10)$$

Figure 2 shows the effect of the S value on the calculation of the analyte concentration. All the data of **Figure 2** was obtained theoretically using equation 10. Three deviations of the true slope are displayed for comparison, representing 1, 5 and 10% of deviation. It is evident that high slope values will lead to greater

1
2
3 concentration bias, *e.g.*, for slope of 0.7, a 10% deviation in the experimental
4 calculation of such parameter leads to a difference of approx. 43% in terms of
5 concentration. **Figure 2** shows the curves up to a slope of 0.8 only, because the
6 concentration bias grows substantially for higher values when a 10% deviation in
7 the calculation of the slope is assumed: for a slope of 0.90, the concentration bias
8 rises up to 1000%. In fact, for high deviations and high slopes the model proposed
9 in equation 8 will eventually fail, as the denominator $(1 - S - e_S)$ may become
10 negative, which makes no sense as such error is defined as positive.
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20

21 In any case, these extremely high deviations for high slopes can be
22 explained simply by analyzing equation 5, because as the slope gets closer to 1,
23 the value $(1-S)$ gets closer to zero and any small difference in the estimation of S
24 leads to a large difference in terms of $(S/1-S)$. For instance, for a true value of S
25 = 0.9, obtaining a calculated value of 0.909 represents a difference of only 1%.
26 However, this variation will lead to a $(S/1-S)$ value of 9.99, instead of the true
27 value of 9. Thus, a difference of only 1% is transformed into a final difference of
28 11% in terms of $(S/1-S)$. Therefore, when designing the experiments with high S
29 values, higher deviations are expected, which would lead to inaccuracies if only
30 one replicate is performed, and to higher irreproducibility when several replicates
31 are carried out.
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45

46 **Figure 2** suggests that using lower slopes (when the amount of analyte in
47 the spike is several times higher than in the sample) would be recommended
48 because the bias will be lower, which in theory is correct. However, such situation
49 could lead to another source of error. For low slopes, the concentration of the
50 analyte in the sample gets to be so low that it shows a minimal influence on the
51 analytical signal, which is certainly not desirable. This effect will be further
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 discussed in Section 3.2. Virgilio *et al.*²⁴ recently shown experimentally that use
4 of “extreme conditions” for the slope (≤ 0.1 or ≥ 0.9) results in lower trueness.
5
6

7
8 Clearly, the deviation of the MEC slope can lead to a miscalculation of the
9
10 analyte concentration, as it also occurs for other more conventional calibration
11
12 strategies. However, MEC also presents another issue that should be considered
13
14 carefully. The concept of MEC is to plot a graph of instrumental responses
15
16 (analytical signals), sample (y-axis) vs. sample+standard (x-axis), measured at
17
18 different wavelengths and use linear regression to calculate the slope, which is
19
20 later substituted in equation 5 to calculate the sample concentration. Therefore,
21
22 the variables represented in both graph axes show uncertainties associated with
23
24 the measurements when using MEC, unlike what occurs in a conventional
25
26 calibration, where the error in the x-axis (mass or concentration) can be
27
28 considered as negligible.³ Thus, choosing a suitable linear regression model
29
30 seems recommended. In this work, the software Origin 2019b was used to
31
32 calculate the MEC slope and its standard deviation (which can be readily applied
33
34 for calculating the standard deviation of the analyte content) with a linear fit with
35
36 x error mode, which minimizes the sum of square of error on both x and y
37
38 directions, also known as York Method.³⁴
39
40
41
42
43

44 3.1.2. Multi-energy ratios (MER) 45

46
47 For MEC, the relation of the analytical signal at different wavelengths with
48
49 the concentration is described in equation 3, from which equation 5 is derived.
50
51 Another way to process the data is also possible for which we propose the name
52
53 of multi-energy ratios (MER). Instead of a linear regression, a direct ratio between
54
55 both intensities can be calculated. The concentrations will now be related to the
56
57 ratios (R) of the analytical signals measured at every wavelength (equation 11).
58
59
60

Equation 12 can be derived from equation 11, showing that both ways to process the data, either using the slope (equation 5) or the (equation 12) ratio, are analogous, simply changing the way in which the same data is processed. Therefore, all the considerations made for MEC in Section 3.1.1 are also valid for MER.

$$\frac{I(\lambda_i)^{Sam}}{I(\lambda_i)^{Sam + Std}} = R = \frac{C^{Sam}}{C^{Sam} + C^{Std}} \quad (11)$$

$$C^{Sam} = \frac{RC^{Std}}{(1 - R)} \quad (12)$$

Figure 3 shows an example of the same experimental data treated by both methods, MEC and MER. The measurements of 11 transitions were evaluated, from 624.510 to 625.478 nm (pixels 40, 46, 54, 63, 74, 86, 100, 114, 131, 149 and 168, see **Figure 1A** and **Table 2** for more information). The x-axis of **Figure 3B** shows the detection pixels instead of the wavelengths for practical purposes. In this study, the sample was 10 μL of a 3 mg L^{-1} Br standard solution (30 ng Br) and the sample+standard was 20 μL of the same solution (60 ng Br), representing the addition of 10 μL of spike of 3 mg L^{-1} (Br-spike mass 30 ng). The instrumental conditions used are shown in **Table 1**.

MEC shows good correlation among the data, $r^2 = 0.9986$, and a slope of 0.5515 is calculated with such approach, which deviates by approx. 10% from the theoretically expected slope (0.5). Applying equation 5, the Br sample mass calculated is 36.9 ± 2.6 ng (average value \pm standard deviation), which is 23% biased from the actual mass of 30 ng. On the other hand, the average ratio of all 11 transitions was found to be 0.4863, which applying the MER approach results in a value of 28.9 ± 5.4 ng, a 3.6% difference only from the true mass.

1
2
3 One of the advantages of using the MEC strategy is the possibility to detect
4 and eliminate outliers.¹⁰ Visualizing the residual data plot of **Figure 3A**, it is
5 possible to remove the data from pixels 46, 149 and 168, which would lead to a
6 new linear correlation of $r^2 = 0.9975$ and a slope of 0.5670 ± 0.0157 . In this case,
7 the calculated Br mass of the sample will be even higher, 39.3 ± 2.5 ng. On the
8 other hand, a conventional linear regression using direct weighing errors with all
9 the 11 transitions was also performed, and in that way MEC leads to a $r^2 = 0.9984$
10 and a slope of 0.5146 ± 0.0070 , and an ultimate Br value of 31.8 ± 0.9 ng.
11 Although in this case this simpler linear regression model provides a slope-value
12 that, calculating the concentration, is less biased, we still propose and will use for
13 further data analysis (unless otherwise noted) a regression model that considers
14 the contribution in terms of uncertainty of both axes for calculating the best linear
15 correlation, as it is more correct considering that in both axes absorption
16 measurements are plotted.
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33

34
35 But outliers can also be detected with ease using MER. Evaluating the
36 data for MER in **Figure 3B**, it is clear that the pixels 40 and 54 are far off the ratio
37 average: they differ by 26.6% and 14.4%, respectively, from 0.4863. If they are
38 considered as outliers, the resulting average ratio is 0.5085 ± 0.0194 , equivalent
39 to a Br mass of 31.1 ± 2.2 ng. It can be noted that the values obtained with or
40 without outliers do not differ significantly from the theoretical value of 30 ng
41 (Student's t-test, $t_{\text{exp}} = 0.676 < t_{\text{crit}95\%} = 2.228$, $n=11$; $t_{\text{exp}} = 1.500 < t_{\text{crit}95\%} =$
42 2.306 , $n=9$). Moreover, there is no significant difference between the mean
43 results obtained in both cases (Student's t-test, $t_{\text{exp}} = 1.232 < t_{\text{crit}95\%} = 2.145$,
44 degrees of freedom = 14, two tails, different variance), but a much better precision
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 is achieved if these two values are rejected (Fisher's test, $F_{\text{exp}} = 6.025 > F_{\text{crit}95\%} =$
4
5 4.295, two tails).
6

7
8 Overall, removing outliers is possible with both approaches but it is
9
10 important to emphasize that they are not going to influence MEC and MER results
11
12 to the same degree. In any case, robust statistical approaches that are less
13
14 affected by the occurrence of outliers are available both for performing
15
16 regressions and for calculating the most representative value of a group of data,
17
18 but it is out of the scope of this paper to further discuss such topic.
19
20

21
22 Both strategies, MEC and MER, represent different ways to extract
23
24 analytical information from the same set of data and their distinct behavior will be
25
26 further investigated in this work.
27

28 **3.2. Monitoring CaBr around 625 nm: different intensity transitions**

29

30
31 As discussed in section 3.1.1., there is an analytical limitation when low-
32
33 or high-value slopes are used for MEC and, due to the similarity of the equations,
34
35 MER should be influenced by these extreme values as well. Therefore, it is
36
37 important to verify this behavior experimentally.
38

39
40 The first experiment consisted in evaluating the RSD obtained for the final
41
42 Br concentration by measuring a blank solution, in order to subtract its values at
43
44 each studied wavelength (pixel), and ten different Br masses: 10, 20, 30, 40, 50,
45
46 60, 80, 100, 120 and 150 ng (10 μL of standard solutions diluted accordingly). All
47
48 measurements were done in triplicate. The data was treated as follows: assuming
49
50 10 ng Br is the sample, thus 20 ng Br could be treated as 10 ng Br sample +10
51
52 ng Br spike. This is equivalent of using MEC or MER with a theoretical value $S =$
53
54 $R = 0.5$. Moreover, 20 ng Br could be treated as a sample and compared with 30
55
56 ng Br (10 ng Br spike), with a theoretical S and R of 0.667, and so forth. All the
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 possible combinations were evaluated for both MEC and MER and the results
4 are shown in **Figure 4**. The slope and ratio axes use logarithm scale for better
5 visualization of lower values. In **Figure 4B** a column goes out of scale, with an
6 RSD of 117% (sample Br mass 50 ng with $R = 0.833$), but the maximum of the z-
7 axis was set at 50% in order to use the same axis for both Figures 4A and 4B,
8 thus enabling an immediate comparison.
9

10
11 Both strategies show a similar behavior: for all the Br mass studied, there
12 is an increase in the final RSD at higher slope or ratio values. This fact agrees
13 well with the theoretical values discussed previously for MEC (see **Figure 2**). A
14 quite constant value of RSD through all the slope and ratios was obtained for 10
15 ng of Br because for low slope or ratio values only slight variations are found (as
16 discussed before, the content of the sample hardly influences the signal). The
17 RSDs are generally higher for low sample Br masses due to their proximity to the
18 limits of detection (LOD). The transitions with lower intensities are more prone to
19 be influenced by the instrumental noise and/or baseline fitting, which increase the
20 uncertainty of the measurement at low Br masses.
21
22

23
24 It is also clear that the RSD is usually higher for MER than for MEC. MER
25 weighs all the ratios equally, thus it is more sensitive to suffer from outliers, if no
26 values are excluded. However, MER also provides an intuitive way to understand
27 all the potential issues, as shown in **Figure 5**. **Figure 5A** shows the results for a
28 Br mass of 30 ng in a sample with different spikes (10, 20, 30, 50, 70, 90 and 120
29 ng Br), and it plots the Br mass finally obtained using MEC *versus* the slope
30 calculated experimentally. In this example, as predicted, the use of lower slopes
31 results in lower RSDs (error bars show the standard deviation). However, such
32 low slopes are also accompanied by a higher deviation from the true value. This
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 effect was commented in Section 3.1.1., that lower slopes/ratios values could
4 lead to poorer accuracy due to the non-optimal relation between sample and
5 spike. The same effect is observed in other strategies such as standard addition
6 and isotope dilution, where it is well-known that the relation between spike and
7 sample contents should be close to one, if possible.
8
9

10
11
12 For MER, a similar trend can be seen for the ratios: use of higher values
13 lead to higher uncertainties, (see the small graph inside **Figure 5B**). However, if
14 each individual value (the ratio of each transition) is plotted (see **Figure 5B**), it is
15 possible to visualize a zone with a high-density of similar ratios (similar Br mass).
16 If only those values are selected, the final results will be closer to MEC results.
17 Moreover, observing $R = 0.6$, the Br mass is 35.2 ± 18.3 ng considering all the
18 data. Obviously, there is an outlier with a value of approximately 85 ng, 2.5 times
19 higher than the average and exceeding the average value plus 2 standard
20 deviations. Eliminating this data with a Dixon's Q test ($Q_{\text{exp}} = 0.825 > Q_{\text{crit}95\%} =$
21 0.466 , $n=10$), the final value changes to 29.5 ± 3.6 ng, which obviously represents
22 much better accuracy and precision. As discussed before, we do not want to
23 complicate too much this topic and to carry out any unfair comparison, but simpler
24 robust estimators (use of median and quartiles; use of the trimmed mean and the
25 robust standard deviation) could and probably should be used for MER instead
26 of relying on tests to reject outliers.
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48

49 In conclusion, while Virgilio *et al.* recommended using slope values
50 between 0.1 and 0.9 for MIP OES, ICP OES and ICP-MS,²⁴ it seems advisable
51 to limit this range more and use values between 0.5 and 0.6 in the case of
52 monitoring CaBr using HR CS GFMS for both MEC and MER strategies to
53 guarantee a well-balanced relation between accuracy and precision.
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

3.3. Effect of analyte-mass linearity for MEC and MER. Figures of merit

It is already well-known that AAS and MAS measurements obey the Lambert-Beer Law, but only for a relatively narrow range of masses. A linear relation between the analytical signal and the analyte mass can be established for one, or maximum two orders of magnitude. It is already well-established what this concept means when external calibration is deployed (*e.g.* need for diluting samples that provide a signal outside the linear range): However, it is necessary to also discuss what this fact represents when trying to use MEC or MER.

Figure 6 shows the response of the HR CS GFMS instrument (integrated absorbance) for several masses of Br, between 20 and 400 ng ($n=8$), monitoring CaBr molecule, at the 11 transitions evaluated in the previous sections around 625 nm. The calibration curves for the most sensitive transitions show linearity until approximately 120 ng (other experiments show that 150 ng is still a safe value) and they lose linearity for a higher Br mass. Less sensitive transitions seem to show linearity in other ranges,³³ from 120 or 200 to 400 ng and probably more, but notice that such linearities (*e.g.*, from 200 to 400 for pixels 131, 114 and 100) do not necessarily go through the intercept. That means that this second range of linearity could be used for external calibration,³⁵ but not for MEC or MER as the equations shown in sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.2 will not be valid.

It is thus important to stress that lack of linearity may affect the determination of the analyte concentration by MEC and MER. Both methods rely on a linear and constant relation between the analyte and the instrumental signal regardless of the amount, *i.e.*, if one of the contents falls outside of the linear range, the calculations should be incorrect, as both contents (sample, and sample plus standard) will obey to different analyte vs. mass relations. The fact that the

1
2
3 linear range may be different for different transitions may be taken into account
4
5 when designing the experiments, and eventually may minimize the number of
6
7 transitions that should be used for a particular analyte amount.
8
9

10 Another limitation for using some lines depending on the analyte amount
11
12 is the limit of quantification (LOQ). The traditional method for calculating LOD and
13
14 LOQ is three and ten times the standard deviation (SD) of ten measurements of
15
16 blank divided by the calibration curve slope, respectively. Using this approach,
17
18 the LOD and LOQ of each wavelength (pixel) previously studied were calculated
19
20 and the results are shown in **Table 3**, labelled as external calibration (EC). The
21
22 LOD of pixel 168 which corresponds to the wavelength 625.315 nm, the usual
23
24 analytical line studied for Br determination *via* CaBr molecule, was 3 ng,
25
26 comparable to the values found in the literature for such transition (between 2.0
27
28 and 5.4 ng),^{33,36,37} all higher than the value of 78 pg achieved by Limburg &
29
30 Einax.³⁸
31
32
33

34
35 LOD and LOQ definitions can also be applied in combination with the MER
36
37 strategy. A blank signal plus $3SD_{10\text{blank}}$ or $10SD_{10\text{blank}}$ is considered as the signal
38
39 of the sample, and equation 11 is used to calculate R for each transition and each
40
41 spike used. Then equation 12 is applied to estimate the LODs and LOQs. These
42
43 values are also shown in **Table 3**. Three Br spikes were chosen for this purpose:
44
45 20, 80 and 150 ng
46
47
48

49 Calculating the LOD and LOQ for MEC is, however, not equally
50
51 straightforward. It requires the calculation of the slope through linear regression,
52
53 comparing two analytical signals, sample and sample+standard, to later apply
54
55 equation 5. In this case, the “sample” is the blank solution that by definition is the
56
57 absence of analyte, *i.e.*, there is practically no analytical signal under normal
58
59
60

1
2
3 conditions. In the x-axis, intensity values proportional to the sensitivity of each
4 transition due to the spike (blank+standard) will be plotted, while the y-axis should
5 provide almost random intensity values due to the blank. Therefore, a linear
6 correlation cannot be expected (see **Figure S1**).
7
8
9

10
11
12 Very recently, Virgilio *et al.* have proposed a method for calculating
13 LOD/LOQ for multi-signal calibrations, including MEC.²⁴ The authors use
14 equation 13 to calculate the LOD/LOQ, where S_{Slope} is the standard deviation of
15 the MEC slope, and N is 3 when calculating the LOD, and 10 for the LOQ. Thus,
16 this strategy was also investigated, and the results are shown in **Table 4**.
17
18
19
20
21
22
23

$$LOD \text{ or } LOQ = N \left(\frac{C^{Std} S_{Slope}}{(1 - Slope)^2} \right) \quad (13)$$

24
25
26
27
28 Four different strategies were evaluated with this approach. Calculation
29 by: i) using the 11 transitions around 625 nm (see **Table 2**); ii) using the three
30 most sensitive transitions (pixels 131, 149 and 168); iii) using the same 11 pixels
31 as in i), but considering Slope = 0; and iv) using the same 3 pixels as in ii), but
32 considering Slope = 0. The first strategy is similar to the one proposed by Virgilio
33 *et al.*²⁴ The second uses equation 13 with the minimum number of different
34 transitions recommended for a MEC analysis, which is three, as discussed by
35 Donati & Amais.³ The third and fourth ones are estimations based on the following
36 concept. As discussed before, MEC should compare two analytical signals, but
37 in this case, one corresponds to a blank solution that shows a random behavior.
38 Thus, the data plotted would hardly follow any linear tendency (see **Figure S1** for
39 examples). It is not evident that the slope resulting from such calculation would
40 possess any physical meaning. Therefore, we assume that a theoretical perfect
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 blank should result in a slope value of zero, and the estimation of LOD/LOQ
4
5 should only account for the uncertainty of the slope measurement.
6
7

8 As shown in **Table 3**, the LODs and LOQs calculated for MER 80 and MER
9
10 150 are, for the most sensitive wavelengths, comparable to those obtained using
11
12 EC. This can be explained because using the method described for calculating
13
14 the LOD/LOQ for MER is analogue to using a one-point calibration curve, which
15
16 would be the spike, since the signal from the blank solution should be negligible
17
18 in comparison with the signal of the spike. Following the same argument, MER
19
20 20 probably has a bit “higher slope” (linearity is never perfect), leading to lower
21
22 values of LOD/LOQ.
23
24

25
26 MER 150 shows lower LOD/LOQ values at low-sensitive wavelengths than
27
28 MER 80. That could have been expected, as higher analytical signals should be
29
30 less affected by random events. Moreover, comparing the previous strategies for
31
32 the most sensitive transitions (**Table 3**, pixel 168) with the LOD/LOQ calculated
33
34 with equation 13 for MEC using first and third strategies, both making use of 11
35
36 transitions (see **Table 4**), they are all rather similar.
37
38

39
40 In any case, we believe that calculating LODs and LOQs using the MER
41
42 approach is always useful to assess which lines should be considered and which
43
44 rejected as a function of the analyte content. On the other hand, when providing
45
46 the overall figure of merit, a method should not have various limits, and a suitable
47
48 strategy to calculate the global LOD and LOQ should be proposed for MER. As
49
50 mentioned above, Donati & Amais³ stated that at least three transitions are
51
52 needed to use MEC, and in this case we will follow the same criteria for MER.
53
54 Therefore, it is reasonable that the three most sensitive analytical lines should be
55
56 considered for calculating the overall LOD/LOQ.
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 Pixel 131 ($\lambda = 625.128$ nm) measures the third most sensitive transition in
4 this region, with a relative sensitivity of 58% compared with the highest peak
5 (625.315 nm). However, during the analysis, an unidentified molecule (see
6 **Figure 7**) was observed when only the blank solution was monitored with both
7 chemical modifier (Pd) and molecule-forming reagent (Ca). This molecule was
8 generated only when the graphite furnace was new and calcium was used. Due
9 to the refractory nature of this molecule (wide-time profile and low intensity), it
10 could be a calcium oxide polyatomic molecule, which has been reported to show
11 a transition at 625.85 nm.³⁹ The interfering molecule could not be eliminated with
12 background least-square correction, available from the AspectCS software, and
13 it especially hampers the measurement at 625.128 nm. Integrating the first 2 s of
14 signal only minimizes the effect of this overlap for the CaBr analytical signal, an
15 approach that was used throughout this study whenever this interfering molecule
16 was detected. Moreover, it is visible that the baseline in this region (see **Figure**
17 **7**) shows a “wavy” profile, which may also influence the determination of peak
18 relations, especially the ones with low intensity. Overall, pixel 114 ($\lambda = 625.045$
19 nm) was used as the third most sensitive line for the current method instead of
20 pixel 131 ($\lambda = 625.128$ nm).
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43

44 Obviously, the overall limits are finally restricted by the highest LOD/LOQ
45 values of the three, *i.e.*, pixel 114 at 625.045 nm. Consequently, in this case we
46 propose a LOD and LOQ of 6 ng and 21 ng, respectively, for the MER strategy.
47 Both figures of merit can be calculated directly as explained without needing any
48 external standard calibration to obtain this value. Nevertheless, using lower
49 amount of spike could be a strategy to improve a bit the LOD and LOQ.
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 Using the same hypothesis for equation 13 (use of the 3 most sensitive
4 transitions only), the values varied from 10 and 33 to 14 and 48 for LOD and LOQ,
5 respectively (see **Table 4**). Assuming a slope value of blank as zero, the limits
6 are practically identical, as the slope is very low in comparison with 1.
7
8
9

10
11
12 In principle, as mentioned by Virgilio *et al.*²⁴ these multi-signal methods will
13 typically show higher values of LOD/LOQ compared to external standard
14 calibration all things considered, as for EC only the most sensitive line is used
15 and for these approaches more, less sensitive and more noisy lines need to be
16 used. However, the difference between MEC and MER here is that, at least
17 applying the equations proposed in ref. 24, MEC benefits from the use of more
18 transitions as lower LODs and LOQs are provided then (see **Table 4**). This is a
19 bit paradoxical, as those extra transitions added offer poorer sensitivity.
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29

30 Overall, we would recommend simply using MER for calculating the LODs
31 and LOQs of the lines tested, as such approach provides useful information for
32 selecting the most suitable ones according to the sample concentration. Such
33 criteria will be used in the next sections to select the lines for the determinations
34 intended.
35
36
37
38
39
40
41

42 **3.4. Monitoring CaBr around 600 nm: similar intensity transitions**

43
44 Considering the results shown in section 3.2., MEC could be considered
45 as a bit more suitable as calibration strategy for CaBr molecule detection using
46 HR CS GFMS around 625 nm mainly because it leads to lower RSD values.
47 The mean value of Br mass obtained by both MEC and MER are similar, and for
48 both strategies is advisable to work in the vicinity of $S = R = 0.5$.
49
50
51
52
53
54
55

56 However, the vibronic transition studied in that section, $X^2\Sigma \rightarrow A^2\Pi (0,0)$,³⁹
57 shows an interesting profile where lines with increasing intensities appear. This
58
59
60

1
2
3 is not always the case. For other molecules monitored by HR CS MAS for the
4 determination of non-metals (e.g., CS, widely proposed to determine S,^{17,28,40} or
5 PO, used to determine P^{17,28,41}) this behavior is not encountered, but instead
6 many lines of similar sensitivity are measured.⁴² Interestingly, this other type of
7 profile can also be investigated measuring CaBr as well. There is another vibronic
8 transition for the CaBr molecule, $X^2\Sigma \rightarrow B^2\Sigma (1,0)$, which appears around 600.24
9 nm and has been previously explored for isotopic analysis.⁴³ In this region, all the
10 transitions of CaBr show similar intensities when Br is found in the natural
11 composition (50.7% ⁷⁹Br and 49.3% ⁸¹Br), except for two larger peaks at 600.321
12 and 600.426 nm where there is an overlap from the transitions of Ca⁷⁹Br and
13 Ca⁸¹Br (thus, practically a double signal is measured; see **Figure 1B** where these
14 overlapped lines are labelled in red). Therefore, this region was studied with MEC
15 and MER to evaluate their performance in this context.

16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Seventeen peaks were selected between 600.115 and 600.835 nm (all the pixels but the two larger ones; see **Figure 1B**). The temperature and chemical modifiers are the same listed in **Table 1**, and the results are displayed in **Figure 8**.

The small differences on the peak intensities reveal a major effect on the signal relations in MEC (see **Figure 8A**), which was already observed for CS, PO and NO molecules using HR CS MAS with flame as atomizer, as several transitions needed to be excluded to improve the linearity.¹⁷ Overall, there is a linear tendency, $r^2 = 0.9583$, but not all the points follow well the trend, and visually there is no easy criteria to select which outliers could be removed. The problem is that all those points in practice behave like three or four different groups of points, instead of like a high number of points more or less evenly

1
2
3 distributed along the line, like in **Figure 3A**. In this case, the theoretical slope and
4 ratio is 0.5. The slope obtained (0.5725 ± 0.0350) resulted in a Br mass of $134 \pm$
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
19 ng, which is 34% biased high. If we include in the regression both pixels 59
and 84 (600.321 and 600.426 nm, respectively, red-labelled peaks in **Figure 1B**)
that show more sensitivity (lines for which Ca^{79}Br and Ca^{81}Br signals overlap),
the MEC slope approximates better to the true value as 0.5364 ± 0.0220 ($116 \pm$
10 ng Br) is obtained, further supporting the concept that the MEC approach
benefits from a higher sensitivity variation between lines (see **Figure 8B**).

When the MER approach is followed (see **Figure 8C**), the small difference
between line sensitivities does not appear to show any clear influence for this
strategy, as could be expected. Using more ratios provides a more robust
estimation. The ratio estimated, 0.5234 ± 0.0313 , is converted to 110 ± 14 ng Br,
with a bias of 10%, which is in any case within the precision of the measurements.

In conclusion, it is possible to assume that MEC could be usually
recommended as a calibration strategy, unless the available transitions show
similar sensitivities, a situation where MER should be considered instead.

3.5. Non-spectral interference

As discussed before, both strategies show higher limits of detection
compared to external standard calibration, but they can help in detecting the
occurrence of spectral overlaps at distinct transitions, which should result in
outliers. Moreover, MEC and MER show potential to correct for matrix effects with
only two solutions, in a similar way as what occurs with isotopic dilution,^{43,44} or
with standard addition (even though for the latter more points are usually
prepared and measured to minimize the uncertainty of the final results when
extrapolating).

1
2
3 A common problem in the case of HR CS MAS is the occurrence of
4 interferences due to chemical competition with other species present in the
5 matrix, affecting the formation of the target species. In the case of monitoring the
6 diatomic molecule CaBr, there are two possibilities: the presence of species that
7 interact with Br, not leaving it available to Ca (e.g., Al) or the presence of species
8 that react with Ca (e.g., other halogens), which would eventually lead to the same
9 effect: formation of less CaBr.⁴³

10
11
12 One of the elements more commonly present in a sample at sufficiently
13 high levels to compromise the formation of the CaBr diatomic molecule is Cl.
14 Nakadi *et al.*⁴³ already studied the interference of chlorine on the determination
15 of Br *via* the monitoring of the CaBr molecule by HR CS GFMAS. In that work,
16 the presence of Cl resulted in 80% of sensitivity loss for the signal of CaBr when
17 it was found at an amount (in moles) 10 times higher than Br. The problem was
18 circumvented using isotopic dilution as calibration strategy, a powerful approach,
19 but one that requires looking for alternative, less sensitive transitions that show
20 sufficiently high isotopic shifts, besides the use of an isotopic spike.

21
22 Under these circumstances, use of MEC and MER could be a more
23 general way to compensate for this effect, because the change in the analytical
24 signal caused by the presence of Cl should be proportionally the same in the
25 sample and in the sample plus the spike, and thus the slope/ratio should be
26 constant.

27
28 To evaluate this hypothesis, a 30 ng standard solution of Br was used as
29 sample and CaBr was monitored around 625 nm. Four Br spikes were studied
30 (10, 20, 30 and 40 ng Br) with three different Cl spikes: 0, 500 and 1000 ng of Cl
31 as sodium chloride. Both MEC and MER were compared for each set of data,
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 and the results are shown in **Figure 9**. Four pixels were used for this study (both
4 MEC and MER), namely 114, 131, 149 and 168, due to their figures of merit, as
5
6 the rest of the pixels did not provide a $LOQ \leq 30$ ng (see **Table 3**).
7
8

9
10 Evaluating pixel 168 ($\lambda = 625.308$ nm), there was a 35% decrease in the
11 CaBr analytical signal when 500 ng Cl were added, and 54% for 1000 ng Cl.
12
13 Nonetheless, using MEC (blue bars) and MER (yellow bars) it is possible to
14
15 circumvent this interference, as can be seen in **Figure 9**. It is noteworthy that, as
16
17 described previously, working at a slope/ratio around 0.5 usually leads to better
18
19 accuracy (difference with the true value lower than 8% considering all Cl masses)
20
21 Opting for a lower slope/ratio (0.4), results biased high seem to be obtained, while
22
23 for a slope/ratio of 0.75 the results are a bit biased low. In this case, using four
24
25 transitions only produces increased RSD values for MEC in comparison with
26
27 MER, as could be appreciated in the error bars of **Figure 9**.
28
29
30
31
32

33 Overall, both strategies were successful in correcting for the Cl
34
35 interference in this study. Nevertheless, it seems advisable to carry out a previous
36
37 study to have an approximate idea of the sample content before spiking it, or
38
39 either to test various spikes to finally work with that providing a slope/ratio close
40
41 to 0.5 - 0.6.
42
43
44

45 **3.6. Determination of Br in water sample using MEC and MER**

46
47 A CRM water (QC3060) was used to evaluate how both strategies can
48
49 correct for the occurrence of interferences and validate the method in a complex
50
51 matrix. This CRM provides the concentration of bromide (2.81 ± 0.42 mg L⁻¹) in
52
53 addition of several anions, such as the halogens chloride (54.9 ± 8.2 mg L⁻¹) and
54
55 fluoride (2.52 ± 0.38 mg L⁻¹), and others with higher concentrations as nitrate
56
57 (66.1 ± 9.9 mg L⁻¹) and sulfate (81.5 ± 12.2 mg L⁻¹). Five transitions were
58
59
60

1
2
3 evaluated (pixels 100, 114, 131, 149 and 168) around 625 nm, pipetting 20 μL of
4
5 the sample (56.2 ± 8.4 ng Br) instead of 10 μL to increase the signal, with three
6
7 Br spikes of 20.4, 58.3 and 96.6 ng. The results obtained are listed in **Table 5**.
8
9

10 Using external standard calibration (calibration range 20 – 100 Br ng, 5
11
12 points, $r^2 = 0.9993$, $\lambda = 625.315$ nm), the Br concentration was calculated to be
13
14 0.282 ± 0.022 mg L^{-1} , which represents only around 10% of recovery, further
15
16 highlighting the influence of the concomitant species. As predicted, using a
17
18 slope/ratio close to 0.5 leads to better values with both MEC and MER, with RSDs
19
20 of 15% and 8%, and a deviation of the average value of only 5.6% and 1.5%,
21
22 respectively, well within the uncertainty of the measurements.
23
24
25

26 In any case, all the conditions evaluated lead to results that overlap with
27
28 the expected value. However, for a 0.75 slope/ratio value, the uncertainty remains
29
30 higher than the others (in particular for MEC), demonstrating that high slopes
31
32 should be avoided. Despite this high uncertainty at 0.75, use of MEC provides
33
34 practically the same average value for all the spikes, proving its robustness.
35
36
37

38 MEC was also evaluated with conventional least-squares regression
39
40 (MEC_Y) for further comparison. Both MEC strategies lead to similar average
41
42 results, although the uncertainty is larger when using York method (see 3.1.1.),
43
44 as expected, because the error sources from both axes are considered in such
45
46 case. Such difference becomes more relevant when using high S values ($S \cong$
47
48 0.75).
49
50
51

52 Overall, all strategies, when properly optimized, enable circumventing
53
54 these non-spectral interferences caused by competing species, supporting their
55
56 use as a valuable alternative method of calibration when performing HR CS
57
58 GFMAS.
59
60

4. Conclusions

The limitations and application of the MEC calibration strategy for determining non-metals *via* HR CS GFMAS was verified in this study, using CaBr as a proxy. Moreover, another similar approach that only differs in the way in which the data is processed (MER) was proposed and evaluated as well for the first time, comparing its performance with that of MEC in different circumstances.

This work confirms previous reports indicating that MEC is a useful tool as a calibration alternative due to its advantage of needing only the preparation and measurement of two aliquots (sample, and sample plus spike) to determine the analyte concentration. Furthermore, this study presents some new conclusions for the best use of both MEC and MER: i) use of too high or too low slope/ratios is not recommended, and values between 0.5 and 0.6 should be chosen; ii) MEC could provide better precision, but its use is favored when many transitions of dissimilar sensitivity are available; if, on the other hand, the transitions available are only a few or show similar sensitivities, the use of MER can provide better results. Furthermore, the calculation of LODs and LOQs using MER is proposed, as it enables checking which lines are above these limits for any particular determination. In any case, it should always be remembered that both the analyte contents of the sample and of the sample plus standard should fall within the working linear range for all the lines considered.

The measurements were hampered mainly by the wavy baseline and occasional appearance of an unknown molecule, as well as by the occurrence of chemical interferences that prevented the quantitative formation of CaBr. Nevertheless, accurate results could be obtained for both MEC and MER, under optimal conditions, proving that these can be very valuable analytical tools for HR

CS GFMS. Moreover, this conclusion can be expanded to other techniques that are prone to be affected by similar issues, and where several different analytical signals can be derived from a single analyte.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to project PGC2018-093753-B-I00 (MCIU/AEI//FEDER, UE), to the European Regional Development Fund for financial support through the Interreg POCTEFA 176/16/DBS, and to the Aragon Government (Construyendo Europa desde Aragón). Raúl Garde acknowledges his predoctoral grant BES-2016-078971 (associated to project CTQ2015-64684-P) from the Ministerio español de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades.

References

1. B. V. L'Vov, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 1988, **3**, 9–12.
2. A. Hulanicki, *Anal. Proc.*, 1992, **29**, 512–516.
3. G. L. Donati and R. S. Amais, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2019, **34**, 2353–2369.
4. J. A. Carter, A. I. Barros, J. A. Nóbrega and G. L. Donati, *Front. Chem.*, 2018, **6**, 504.
5. P. Kościelniak and J. Kozak, *Crit. Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 2006, **36**, 27–40.
6. J. E. T. Andersen, *TrAC - Trends Anal. Chem.*, 2017, **89**, 21–33.
7. F. Vanhaecke, L. Balcaen and D. Malinovsky, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2009, **24**, 863–886.
8. P. Rodríguez-González, J. M. Marchante-Gayón, J. I. García Alonso and A. Sanz-Medel, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B*, 2005, **60**, 151–207.
9. K. G. Heumann, S. M. Gallus, G. Rädlinger and J. Vogl, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 1998, **13**, 1001–1008.
10. A. Virgilio, D. A. Gonçalves, T. McSweeney, J. A. Gomes Neto, J. A. Nóbrega and G. L. Donati, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2017, **982**, 31–36.
11. R. C. Machado, A. B. S. Silva, G. L. Donati and A. R. A. Nogueira, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2018, **33**, 1168–1172.
12. D. V. Babos, A. Virgilio, V. C. Costa, G. L. Donati and E. R. Pereira-Filho, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2018, **33**, 1753–1762.
13. A. S. Augusto, J. P. Castro, M. A. Sperança and E. R. Pereira-Filho, *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.*, 2019, **30**, 804–812.
14. D. F. Andrade, F. M. Fortunato and E. R. Pereira-Filho, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2019, **1061**, 42–49.

15. F. M. Fortunato, T. A. Catelani, M. S. Pomares-Alfonso and E. R. Pereira-Filho, *Anal. Sci.*, 2019, **35**, 165–168.
16. A. A. C. Carvalho, L. A. Cozer, M. S. Luz, L. C. Nunes, F. R. P. Rocha and C. S. Nomura, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2019, **34**, 1701–1707.
17. A. L. Vieira, D. A. Gonçalves, A. Virgílio, E. C. Ferreira, B. T. Jones, G. L. Donati and J. A. Gomes Neto, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2019, **34**, 972–978.
18. M. C. Alencar, D. A. Gonçalves, G. Nicolodelli, S. L. Oliveira, G. L. Donati and A. R. L. Caires, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2019, 117221.
19. A. Virgílio, J. A. Nóbrega and G. L. Donati, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2018, **410**, 1157–1162.
20. J. M. de Higuera, A. B. S. da Silva, A. F. de Oliveira and A. R. de Araujo Nogueira, *Food Chem.*, 2020, **303**, 125395.
21. E. Bolea-Fernandez, L. Balcaen, M. Resano and F. Vanhaecke, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2017, **32**, 1660–1679.
22. L. Balcaen, E. Bolea-Fernandez, M. Resano and F. Vanhaecke, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2015, **894**, 7–19.
23. C. B. Williams and G. L. Donati, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2018, **33**, 762–767.
24. A. Virgílio, A. B. S. Silva, A. R. A. Nogueira, J. A. Nobrega and G. L. Donati, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2020, **35**, 1614–1620.
25. B. Welz, H. Becker-Ross, S. Florek and U. Heitmann, High-resolution Continuum Source AAS. The Better Way to Do Atomic Absorption Spectrometry, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2005.
26. M. Resano, M. Aramendía and M. A. Belarra, *J Anal Spectrom*, 2014, **29**, 2229–2250.
27. M. Resano, E. García-Ruiz, M. Aramendía and M. A. Belarra, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2019, **34**, 59–80.
28. M. Resano, M. Aramendía, F. V. Nakadi, E. García-Ruiz, C. Alvarez-Llamas, N. Bordel, J. Pisonero, E. Bolea-Fernández, T. Liu and F. Vanhaecke, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.*, 2020, **129**, 115955.
29. M. Resano, L. Rello, M. Flórez and M. A. Belarra, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B*, 2011, **66**, 321–328.
30. M. Resano, M. R. Flórez and E. García-Ruiz, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B*, 2013, **88**, 85–97.
31. B. Welz, F. G. Lepri, R. G. O. Araujo, S. L. C. Ferreira, M. D. Huang, M. Okruss and H. Becker-Ross, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2009, **647**, 137–148.
32. M. Resano, M. R. Flórez and E. García-Ruiz, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2014, **406**, 2239–2259.
33. M. R. Flórez and M. Resano, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B*, 2013, **88**, 32–39.
34. <https://www.originlab.com/doc/Origin-Help/LinearFit-XErr-Dialog>, accessed in 2020, July 14th
35. B. Welz, L. M. G. dos Santos, R. G. O. Araujo, S. do C. Jacob, M. G. R. Vale, M. Okruss and H. Becker-Ross, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B*, 2010, **65**, 258–262.
36. M. D. Huang, H. Becker-Ross, S. Florek, U. Heitmann and M. Okruss, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B*, 2008, **63**, 566–570.
37. É. R. Pereira, I. N. B. Castilho, B. Welz, J. S. Gois, D. L. G. Borges, E. Carasek and J. B. De Andrade, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B*, 2014, **96**, 33–39.
38. T. Limburg and J. W. Einax, *Microchem. J.*, 2013, **107**, 31–36.
39. R. W. B. Pearse and A. G. Gaydon, The Identification of Molecular Spectra, fourth ed., Chapman and Hall Ltd., London, 1976.
40. N. Ozbek and A. Baysal, *TrAC - Trends Anal. Chem.*, 2017, **88**, 62–76.

- 1
2
3 41. L. C. Pomarolli, M. A. M. Silva da Veiga, M. Resano, F. V. Nakadi, *J. Anal.*
4 *At. Spectrom.*, 2020, in press, 10.1039/d0ja00254b
5 42. D. J. Butcher, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2013, **804**, 1–15.
6 43. F. V Nakadi, M. A. M. S. da Veiga, M. Aramendía, E. García-Ruiz and M.
7 Resano, *J Anal Spectrom*, 2016, **31**, 1381–1390.
8 44. F. V. Nakadi, M. A. M. S. da Veiga, M. Aramendía, E. García-Ruiz and M.
9 Resano, *J Anal Spectrom*, 2015, **30**, 1531–1540.
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Table 1. HR CS GFMA conditions for the determination of Br *via* the monitoring of CaBr.

Vibronic transition / Central pixel wavelength	$X^2\Sigma \rightarrow A^2\Pi (0,0)$ / 624.997 nm			
	$X^2\Sigma \rightarrow B^2\Sigma (1,0)$ / 600.492 nm			
Number of detector pixels	5 (CP \pm 2)			
Sample volume / μ L	10, 20*			
Chemical modifier	Pd (30 μ g)			
Molecule-forming reagent	Ca (150 μ g)			
<i>Temperature program</i>				
Step	Temperature / °C	Ramp / °C s ⁻¹	Hold / s	Ar gas flow / L min ⁻¹
Drying	90	5	20	2.0
Drying	120	5	30	2.0
Pyrolysis	1000	50	20	2.0
Gas adaption	1000	0	5	0.0
Vaporization	2100	3000	4-6**	0.0
Cleaning	2500	500	4	2.0

*used for the determination of Br in the CRM QC3060

** The signal is integrated during the first 2 seconds

Table 2. Relation between the detection pixel number and the wavelength for the vibronic transitions $X^2\Sigma \rightarrow A^2\Pi (0,0)$ and $X^2\Sigma \rightarrow B^2\Sigma (1,0)$ of the CaBr diatomic molecule.

Transition $X^2\Sigma \rightarrow A^2\Pi (0,0)$		Transition $X^2\Sigma \rightarrow B^2\Sigma (1,0)$	
Pixel	Wavelength / nm	Pixel	Wavelength / nm
40	624.685	11	600.115
46	624.714	20	600.153
54	624.753	44	600.253
63	624.797	51	600.283
74	624.850	59*	600.321
86	624.909	68	600.354
100	624.972	74	600.379
114	625.045	84*	600.426
131	625.128	94	600.463
149	625.211	100	600.488
168	625.315	109	600.526
		122	600.580
		127	600.601
		136	600.639
		143	600.668
		151	600.701
		165	600.760
		175	600.802
		183	600.835

*Overlapped peaks

Table 3. Figures of merit corresponding to the CaBr vibronic transition $X^2\Sigma - A^2\Pi$ (0,0) using HR CS GFMAS. External calibration (the calibration curve covered a Br mass range between 10 and 150 ng) is labelled as EC. Each number besides MER corresponds to the Br mass spike, in ng, used for the calculation of LOD and LOQ. Both EC and MER were evaluated using 11 wavelengths (pixels). n.a.: not applied.

Pixel	LOD; LOQ / ng Br			
	<i>EC</i>	<i>MER 20</i>	<i>MER 80</i>	<i>MER 150</i>
40	40; 135	n.a.	86; 286	54; 181
46	52; 174	n.a.	116; 386	70; 235
54	43; 142	n.a.	89; 297	57; 189
63	53; 178	n.a.	143; 476	82; 274
74	22; 72	15; 50	25; 84	23; 77
86	26; 87	25; 84	34; 115	30; 100
100	17; 55	11; 36	18; 61	18; 59
114	6; 21	3; 10	6; 20	6; 21
131	9; 30	4; 15	9; 30	9; 30
149	4; 14	2; 6	4; 13	4; 14
168	3; 11	1; 4	3; 10	3; 10

Table 4. Figures of merit corresponding to the CaBr vibronic transition $X^2\Sigma - A^2\Pi$ (0,0) using HR CS GFMAS and MEC calculated *via* equation 13. N_T represents the number of transitions used for the calculation of the LOD/LOQ, and S is the theoretical value of slope.

Br spike / ng	LOD; LOQ / ng Br			
	$N_T = 11$	$N_T = 3$	$N_T = 11, S = 0$	$N_T = 3, S = 0$
20	3; 9	10; 33	3; 9	10; 32
80	3; 11	13; 43	3; 11	13; 43
150	4; 12	14; 48	4; 12	14; 48

Table 5. Determination of Br in QC3060 *via* the monitoring of CaBr with HR CS GFMS using MEC and MER strategies. Uncertainties are given as 95% confidence intervals (n=5). n.a.: not applied. MEC values are obtained as recommended in this work (see 3.1.1.), while for MEC_γ, conventional linear regression considering only the errors in y-axis was used.

Br mass spike / ng	Slope/Ratio			Br concentration / mg L ⁻¹				Reference
	MEC	MEC _γ	MER	MEC	MEC _γ	MER	EC	
0	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	0.282 ± 0.022	
20.4	0.745 ± 0.116	0.743 ± 0.054	0.716 ± 0.023	2.97 ± 2.10	2.94 ± 0.86	2.57 ± 0.36	n.a.	2.81 ± 0.42
58.3	0.504 ± 0.045	0.504 ± 0.039	0.495 ± 0.020	2.97 ± 0.54	2.96 ± 0.47	2.85 ± 0.29	n.a.	
96.6	0.390 ± 0.036	0.392 ± 0.033	0.376 ± 0.017	3.08 ± 0.47	3.11 ± 0.43	2.91 ± 0.27	n.a.	

Figure captions

Figure 1. Spectra of the CaBr diatomic molecule (A) in the vicinity of 625.0 nm, as obtained with 30 ng Br; and (B) in the vicinity of 600.5 nm, as obtained with 100 ng Br. The numbers over the peaks correspond to the detection pixel at a specific wavelength (see **Table 2**). Graphite furnace conditions are listed in **Table 1**.

Figure 2. Theoretical relation between different deviations from the true slope (1, 5 and 10%, with different shades of blue) and the final bias in the concentration calculated using MEC.

Figure 3. Experimental data (11 transitions) obtained for 30 ng Br as sample and 30 ng Br as spike using HR CS GFMAS for the monitoring of CaBr in the vicinity of 625 nm with (A) MEC and (B) MER strategies. Error bars correspond to the standard deviation (n=3). The labels shown in Figure 3A correspond to the pixels measured

Figure 4. Evaluation of the RSD of the Br masses calculated from standard solutions containing Br ranging 10 to 120 ng with different (A) slopes and (B) ratios using MEC and MER, respectively. In Figure 4B, the RSD value for sample Br mass 50 ng with 0.833 ratio is out of scale (actual value, 117%).

Figure 5. Br determination (true mass 30 ng) through (A) MEC and (B) MER at different slopes/ratios. Each data of Figure 5B shows the mean value for each one of the transition evaluated. The small graph inside Figure 5B shows the overall mean value of all the transitions with its uncertainty. The red line corresponds to the real value (30 ng). The error bars correspond to the standard deviations (n=3).

1
2
3 **Figure 6.** Calibration curves (Br values ranging from 20 to 400 ng) when
4 monitoring the CaBr molecule using HR CS GFMS. The numbers of each
5 calibration curve correspond to the detection pixels (wavelength) used to obtain
6 the integrated absorbance ($CP_{\pm 2}$) of different rotational contributions of the
7 vibronic transition $X^2\Sigma - A^2\Pi (0,0)$. Error bars correspond to the standard
8 deviation ($n=3$).
9

10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17 **Figure 7.** Time- and wavelength-resolved spectrum of the unknown molecular
18 interference appearing in the analytical region around 625 nm.
19

20
21
22 **Figure 8.** Experimental data for 100 ng Br as sample and 100 ng Br as spike
23 using HR CS GFMS *via* monitoring of the CaBr molecule in the vicinity of 600
24 nm using: (A) MEC with 17 transitions; (B) MEC with 19 transitions (the 17 used
25 before plus pixels 59 and 84); and (C) MER with 17 transitions. Error bars
26 correspond to the standard deviation ($n=3$).
27
28
29
30
31

32
33 **Figure 9.** Study of the effect of the presence of Cl on the determination of Br *via*
34 the monitoring of the CaBr molecule with HR CS GFMS using MEC (blue bars)
35 and MER (yellow bars) strategies for quantification. The gray surface indicates
36 the real Br mass (30 ng). Error bars correspond to the standard deviation ($n=5$).
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Development of equations 8 and 9 from equation 7

$$bias_{CSam}^{\pm}(\%) = \frac{\left\{ \frac{(S \pm e_s)}{[1 - (S \pm e_s)]} \right\} - \left(\frac{S}{1-S} \right)}{\left(\frac{S}{1-S} \right)} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

It can be noticed (see equation 6) that the upper limit of e_s value will lead to the upper limit of e_c and concentration bias, e_c^+ and $bias_{CSam}^+$ respectively.

Thus, equation 7 can be further developed as follows.

$$bias_{CSam}^+(\%) = \frac{\left\{ \frac{(S + e_s)}{[1 - (S + e_s)]} \right\} - \left(\frac{S}{1-S} \right)}{\left(\frac{S}{1-S} \right)} \times 100\%$$

$$bias_{CSam}^+(\%) = \frac{\left\{ \frac{[(S + e_s) \times (1 - S)] - [S \times (1 - S - e_s)]}{(1 - S - e_s) \times (1 - S)} \right\}}{\left(\frac{S}{1-S} \right)} \times 100\%$$

$$bias_{CSam}^+(\%) = \frac{(S - S^2 + e_s - Se_s - S + S^2 + Se_s)}{(1 - S - e_s) \times (1 - S)} \times \frac{(1 - S)}{S} \times 100\%$$

$$bias_{CSam}^+(\%) = \frac{e_s}{S(1 - S - e_s)} \times 100\% \quad (8)$$

The lower limit, $bias_{CSam}^-$, can be calculated analogously, resulting in equation 9.

$$bias_{CSam}^-(\%) = \frac{\left\{ \frac{(S - e_s)}{[1 - (S - e_s)]} \right\} - \left(\frac{S}{1-S} \right)}{\left(\frac{S}{1-S} \right)} \times 100\%$$

$$bias_{CSam}^-(\%) = \frac{\left\{ \frac{[(S - e_s) \times (1 - S)] - [S \times (1 - S + e_s)]}{(1 - S + e_s) \times (1 - S)} \right\}}{\left(\frac{S}{1-S} \right)} \times 100\%$$

$$bias_{CSam}^-(\%) = \frac{(S - S^2 - e_s + Se_s - S + S^2 - Se_s)}{(1 - S + e_s) \times (1 - S)} \times \frac{(1 - S)}{S} \times 100\%$$

$$bias_{\bar{c}_{sam}}(\%) = \frac{-e_s}{S(1 - S + e_s)} \times 100\% \quad (9)$$

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Figure S1. Blank measurements vs. 20, 80 and 150 ng Br spikes using MEC for calculating the LOD and LOQ, as described in equation 13.